

Assessing the impact of nationalist parties on the sustainability of democracy: The perceptions of Romanian students in the context of the 2024 European Parliament elections

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of nationalist parties on the sustainability of democracy, focusing on Romanian students' perceptions in the context of the 2024 European Parliamentary elections. The rise of nationalist and populist parties across the European Union has sparked concerns about the potential erosion of democratic values and stability. Using a descriptive exploratory research design, data were collected via an electronically distributed questionnaire from 417 students representing diverse educational and socio-demographic backgrounds. The analysis revealed significant associations between students' socio-demographic factors and their trust in nationalist parties, as well as their perceptions of these parties' impact on democracy. Higher education levels correlated with more pronounced negative perceptions of nationalist parties. Age, gender, residence, education, and socio-economic status also played crucial roles in shaping these perceptions. The findings highlight a moderate awareness among students regarding the under-mining effects of nationalist parties on democracy, with significant concerns about misinformation, political polarization, and the erosion of democratic institutions. The study underscores the need for enhanced civic education and reliable information to foster informed political opinions and sustain democratic values amidst the rising influence of nationalism.

Keywords

Nationalist parties; democracy sustainability; political perceptions; European Parliament elections; Romanian students

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Introduction

In recent years, the European Union (EU) has witnessed a significant increase of nationalism, marked by the rise of nationalist and populist parties in many of its member states (Marin, 2018). This trend is often seen as a reaction to the multiple interconnected challenges faced the region. One of the most pressing challenges is large-scale migration from conflict zones and countries with limited economic opportunities, which has put significant pressure on the resources and social services of many Member States (Dogachan, 2018). This has fueled feelings of insecurity and has been exploited by populist parties to spread anti-immigration rhetoric, exacerbating fears about identity and cultural cohesion. Global economic transformations, including globalization and digitization, have reshaped the labor market, negatively affecting workers in traditional sectors and amplifying feelings of economic alienation (Quirk, 2022). Nationalists and populists have capitalized on these grievances, promoting protectionist policies and criticizing economic and political elites for their detachment from the needs of ordinary citizens. Also, the perceived loss of national sovereignty, in the context of perceived intrusive EU regulation, has been another source of resentment, intensified during crises such as the economic recession, when decisions at EU level have had a direct impact on national economies (Csergő and Goldgeier, 2004).

Taken together, these elements contribute to a possible fundamental reconfiguration not only of Member States' internal policies, but also of the European Union's foreign and security policy. Rising nationalism may undermine solidarity between Member States, undermining EU cohesion and integrity in the long term (Seth, 2015). This dynamic calls for a profound reflection on the future of European integration and on the measures needed to maintain unity in front of these challenges. Moreover, the rise of nationalism may undermine fundamental EU values such as liberalism, pluralism and transnational cooperation. This not only calls for the renegotiation of vital agreements, but also stimulates debates about the future of Europe's political and economic integration. The impact of these parties can have lasting effects on the European political and social structures, directly influencing the direction of public policies and European legislation (Accetti, 2020).

It is crucial to understand how nationalist parties shape democratic principles and sustainability in the European Union, especially in the context of the upcoming European Parliament elections. These elections are a critical moment to assess the growing influence of nationalism on EU politics. A careful analysis of this dynamic can provide valuable insight into how democratic values are perceived and upheld among European citizens and can help to formulate informed policy responses that promote cohesion and stability in the face of emerging challenges (Batory, 2010).

The central problem of this study is to identify and analyze how nationalism influences students' perceptions and voting behavior in the context of the European Parliament elections. In the last decade, nationalism has gained ground in European political discourse, which has led to significant changes in electoral behavior, especially among young people. It is imperative to understand these dynamics to anticipate future electoral trends and assess their impact on the European political and social structures. Therefore, this study aims to explore the extent to which nationalist narratives influence the attitudes and voting intentions of students, an active and influential electoral segment (Hjerm and Schnabel, 2010). Thus, exploring the impact of nationalism is crucial for maintaining the political integrity of the European Union and ensuring a sustainable and inclusive future for all its citizens (Mair, 2007).

This study aims to explore and analyze the impact of nationalist parties on the support of traditional democratic values among Romanian students in the context of the 2024 European Parliament elections. It aims to gain an in-depth understanding of young people's perceptions of

nationalism and how it influences their political beliefs, attitudes towards democracy and electoral participation.

Research hypotheses: (H1): There is a correlation between support for nationalist parties and support for traditional democratic values among Romanian students. (H2): Negative perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on democracy are more pronounced among students with university education compared to those with pre- university education. (H3): Socio-demographic factors such as age, gender and residence (urban vs. rural) significantly influence students' attitudes towards nationalist parties and their perception of their long-term impact on democracy. (H4): Adequate information about policies and their consequences reduces support for nationalist parties, indicating that access to quality and credible information plays a crucial role in shaping students' political opinion.

Specific objectives: (O1): To measure students' level of trust in nationalist parties and to determine the correlations between their trust and support for democratic principles. (O2): To assess students' perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on the stability and sustainability of democracy in Europe, with a focus on potential long-term effects. (O3): To identify determinants influencing students' attitudes and voting behavior towards nationalist parties, including socio-demographic variables and access to information. (O4): Analyze differences in perceptions between different demographic groups (e.g. differences based on age, education, urban vs. rural) to detect specific patterns or trends among young people.

This study is essential in the current context, marked by a growing influence of nationalist parties in many EU Member States, including Romania. Nationalism, often associated with anti-European and anti-immigrant rhetoric, can have a profound impact on social cohesion and the sustainability of liberal democracies. In a period of economic and security uncertainties and social tensions, it is crucial to understand how young people, especially students, perceive these parties and to what extent these perceptions influence their support for fundamental democratic principles.

By exploring the attitudes of Romanian students, the study responds to an acute need for empirical data on how the next generation perceives and interacts with nationalism and democracy. It contributes to the existing literature by focusing on a key demographic cohort that is often neglected in political research - young people - and provides valuable insight into potential changes in the European political landscape on the long term.

Literature review

The rise of nationalism in the European Union is a complex phenomenon that reflects the tensions between supranational integration and consolidated national identities. This dynamic is supported by the persistence of nationalism despite the deepening integration of member states, reflecting the continuous desire for a stronger national voice (Csérgő and Goldgeier, 2004). In this context, nationalist and populist parties have adopted different strategies, such as protectionism and subjective nationalism, as response to the challenges of globalization and migration (Martinelli, 2018).

The trend known as "new nationalism" is characterized by a populist discourse and an emphasis on national sovereignty (Seth, 2015), largely motivated by a cultural reaction to rapid demographic and social changes. These parties promote a 'national preference' in their policies, which has changed the European political landscape (Halikiopoulou and Vlandas, 2019). Although the concept of 'European nationalism' may seem an oxymoron, it reflects the tensions between a supranational European ideal and the persistent nationalist realities that influence EU policy (d'Appollonia, 2002; Quirk, 2022). Thus, while the EU was originally conceived as an antidote to the destructive nationalism of the past, today it faces the challenge of navigating and mediating between

supranational aspirations and the nationalist realities that continue to shape the European political landscape. This duality calls for continued reflection on the future of European integration and the role of national identities within it (Bolles, 1963).

Sustainability in the European Union is deeply intertwined with the state of democracy, as the rise of nationalist parties may threaten the democratic foundations of the Union. This phenomenon, against a backdrop of rising nationalism, puts pressure on democratic principles by promoting isolationist policies and skepticism towards integration, which may weaken traditional democratic mechanisms that underpin long-term sustainability (Arias-Maldonado, 2000; Jakab, 2015; Pe'er et al., 2020).

In the light of recent policies such as the European Green Deal, there is an attempt to harmonize policy discourse with sustainability objectives. However, contradictions between rhetoric and practice highlight a tension between intentions and actions. Critics argue that while the EU strives to be a global leader in sustainability, nationalist tendencies can distort these efforts, diverting resources and attention away from environmental goals to more restrictive policy agendas, which can undermine the effectiveness of the response to global environmental challenges (Hunold, 2005; Eckert and Kowaleska, 2021; Schunz, 2022).

The rise of nationalism erodes the foundations of European democracy by promoting an agenda that limits pluralism and civic participation, essential for democratic sustainability. This trend could restrict civil liberties and limit the participation of civil society in the governance process, which is vital for maintaining an open and transparent governance framework. Weakening these democratic principles could have long-lasting consequences on the Union's ability to implement effective sustainability policies (Hunold, 2005; Jakab, 2015; Eckert and Kowaleska, 2021).

Materials and methods

This analysis uses a descriptive, exploratory research design based on data collection through an electronically distributed questionnaire. The main objective was to assess Romanian students' perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on the sustainability of democracy in the context of the 2024 European Parliament elections.

The research sample consist of 417 students, representative for different educational and socio-demographic backgrounds in Romania. Participation in the study was voluntary and unpaid, and all the subjects were informed about the purpose of the research and about the confidentiality of the collected data, which were anonymized to prevent respondents' identification.

The age distribution² shows a predominance of young people aged 18-22 (46.2% of all participants), followed by the 23-27 age group (33.5%). The other age groups (28-32 and 33+) represent a significantly smaller proportion of the sample. The gender distribution shows a female majority in the first age group (67.8%), while in the other age groups, the distribution is more balanced between women and men. The place of residence is predominantly urban for all age groups, apart from the youngest age group, where the urban percentage is 65.8%, suggesting that a significant number of young people also come from rural areas. Educational level shows a concentration of responses from students, especially in the 18- 22 age group, where 95.3% are students. This is consistent with the fact that most participants in this category are still enrolled in a university degree. Professional status and monthly income reflect a variety of economic and professional situations, with a predominance of students who do not generate significant income. In the 23-27 age group, 70.7% of

² Data regarding the distributions are available from the author, on request.

the participants earn less than 3000 lei per month (600 Euro), indicating a transition from student status to the beginning of a professional career.

The main instrument used in the study was a questionnaire designed using the Google Forms platform. It included questions structured as Likert scales, as well as multiple choice questions, which aimed to assess the level of support for nationalist parties and perceptions of their impact on democratic principles. The questionnaire was distributed electronically using a weblink, allowing for easy redistribution on social networks, which facilitated reaching many respondents.

The questionnaire was accessible to participants for a fixed period (March 15 - April 15, 2024), and access to the questions was conditioned by informed consent granting. This informed consent was presented at the beginning of the questionnaire, and participants had to express their explicit agreement to participate by selecting the response option 'Yes, I agree to participate in the research'. Respondents who did not agree with the terms presented in the informed consent were automatically excluded from the study.

Descriptive analysis was used to summarize the basic characteristics of the sample. This included calculating frequencies, means, standard deviations and other descriptive statistics. The purpose of this analysis was to provide a clear picture of the distribution of the socio-demographic variables of the participants, such as age, gender, residence, education level and employment status.

Multiple linear regression was used to examine the simultaneous influence of several independent variables on a dependent variable. This test identified important predictors and quantified the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable, controlling for the influences of the other variables. The regression model was used to test the research hypotheses and to better understand the complexity of the relationships between the variables under study.

The chi-square test was applied to assess associations between categorical variables. This test is used to determine whether there is a statistically significant relationship between categorical variables, such as gender, residential background or educational level, and student attitudes or perceptions. The chi-square test helps to identify whether the observed distributions of variables are different from those expected by chance. In terms of justifying the choice of tests, each of the statistical tests chosen was selected to respond to the specificities of the research hypotheses and to provide a comprehensive analysis of the data collected. The descriptive analysis provided a clear basis on the distribution of the demographic characteristics of the sample. Correlation and multiple linear regression tests allowed the examination of complex relationships and effects between independent and dependent variables. Chi-square tests were essential to assess associations between categorical variables. These statistical methods were essential to test hypotheses and to provide an in-depth understanding of students' perceptions and attitudes in the context of the influence of nationalist parties on democracy.

The study followed all relevant ethical norms in social research, including confidentiality, anonymity and informed consent. No personally identifiable information was collected as part of the questionnaire, thus ensuring the protection of participants' personal data in accordance with the existing legislation.

Results

Table 1 analyzes the trust in nationalist parties, measured on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest level of trust and 5 the highest. The statistical analysis includes the mean, standard deviation and median for each age group. The 18-22 age group has a mean of 2.55 and a standard deviation of 1.03, with a median of 3. This indicates a moderately dispersed distribution of responses, with a slight

tendency towards a low level of trust in nationalist parties. The range of values (1-5) suggests both very low and some maximum responses, reflecting a variety of perceptions in this age group. The 23-27 age group has a mean of 2.30 and a standard deviation of 1.08, with a median of 2. These figures show an even lower trust in nationalist parties than the previous group, and a similar dispersion of the data. The 28-32 age group shows a mean of 1.77 and a standard deviation of 1.01, with a median of 1.5. This indicates the lowest trust in nationalist parties of all age groups analyzed, with a relatively small dispersion of responses. The 33+ age group has a mean of 2.53 and a standard deviation of 1.02, with a median of 2.5. This group returns to a similar mean value as the youngest group, indicating a mixed perception, with a slight tendency towards moderate trust in nationalist parties.

Table 1. Trust in nationalist parties: descriptive statistics and associations.

Age group	Mean	Std. deviation	Median	%
18-22	2.55	1.03	3	46.2
23-27	2.30	1.08	2	33.5
28-32	1.77	1.01	1.5	11.5
33+	2.53	1.02	2.5	8.6

Variables	Pearson chi-square	df	p-value
Age	29.228	8	.000
Gender	28.413	4	.000
Residence (urban vs. Rural)	9.175	4	.057
Education level	44.639	20	.001
Marital status	26.073	4	.000
Socio-professional status	52.491	12	.000
Monthly income	28.987	16	.024

The chi-square test results reveal significant associations between various socio-demographic variables and the level of trust in nationalist parties. First, there is a significant association between age and trust in nationalist parties. This indicates that different age groups show significantly different levels of trust in nationalist parties, emphasizing that age is a crucial factor influencing political perceptions. Similarly, gender is another variable with a significant association with trust in nationalist parties, this result suggesting there are notable differences between men and women in levels of trust in these parties. Although the association between residence (urban or rural) and trust in nationalist parties did not manage to achieve statistical significance, there may be some differences based on residence. However, this association is not strong enough to be considered statistically significant at the 0.05 level, suggesting that more research is needed to confirm this trend. The level of education shows a significant association with trust in nationalist parties. This result indicates that individuals with different levels of education have different levels of trust in nationalist parties, suggesting that education plays a crucial role in the formation of political opinions. Marital status is another variable that has a significant association with trust in nationalist parties. This result suggests that marital status influences political perceptions and trust in these parties. The socio-professional status of individuals also shows a significant association with trust in nationalist parties. This result emphasizes the importance of socio-economic factors in determining political trust and affiliations. Finally, monthly income shows a significant association with trust in nationalist parties, suggesting that economic status, as indicated by monthly income, affects individuals' levels of trust in nationalist parties.

Table 2. Students' perceptions of nationalist parties undermining democracy in the current European context.

Variable	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient - beta	95% confidence interval for beta
Constant	3.588	0.194	---	3.207 – 3.968
Age	0.527	0.081	0.368	0.368 – 0.686
Marital status	-0.619	0.187	-0.175	-0.986 – -0.252
Income	-0.181	0.058	-0.167	-0.296 – -0.066

Analyzing the data in Table 2, we observe students' perceptions of the level of undermining of democracy by nationalist parties in the current European context. The mean score of 3.54, together with a standard deviation of 1.10, reveals a relatively worrying opinion of young people about the impact of nationalist parties on democratic structures. The average of 3.54 indicates a general perception that nationalist parties have a moderate negative impact on democracy. This score is not extremely high, suggesting that while there are significant concerns, not all respondents see nationalist parties as a major threat. However, the above-average level reflects an awareness of the risks these parties may pose to social cohesion and the integrity of democratic processes. The standard deviation of 1.10 tells us that there is a notable variation in student responses. This variation can be attributed to differences in perception based on personal factors, educational factors, or direct experiences with nationalist party politics and rhetoric. Some young people may perceive a greater threat, while others may be more skeptical about the actual impact of these parties on democracy.

This diversity of views reflects the complexity of political interpretations and assessments in a dynamic and often polarized political climate. While most students recognize some degree of negative impact, the degree of this impact varies, highlighting the need for further discussion and critical analysis to better understand the reasons behind these perceptions. Appreciation of the level of undermining of democracy by nationalist parties is the dependent variable analyzed using multiple linear regression. The results indicate that the age of the respondents has a positive and significant influence on this variable, with an unadjusted coefficient of 0.527 and significance $p < 0.001$. This suggests that older respondents perceive a higher level of undermining of democracy by nationalist parties. In contrast, marital status has a negative and significant influence on the assessment of the level of undermining of democracy, with an unadjusted coefficient of -0.619 and significance $p < 0.001$. This indicates that respondents who are married or in a stable relationship perceive less undermining of democracy by nationalist parties compared to those who are unmarried. Respondents' monthly income also has a negative and significant influence on the dependent variable, with an unadjusted coefficient of -0.181 and significance $p < 0.002$. This result suggests that higher income earners perceive a lower level of undermining of democracy by nationalist parties.

Table 3. Perceived impact of nationalist parties on democracy.

Variables	Pearson chi-square	df	p-value
Age	46.612	6	0.000
Gender	35.045	3	0.000
Residence (urban vs. Rural)	3.005	3	0.391
Education level	43.374	15	0.000
Marital status	36.992	3	0.000
Socio-professional status	36.69	9	0.000
Monthly income	42.063	12	0.000

Table 3 presents participants' perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on democracy. A considerable proportion of respondents (34.7%) believe that nationalist parties undermine democracy. This perception could indicate concerns about the influence of these parties on the stability and integrity of democratic processes. Half of the participants (50.3%) identified a mixed impact. This suggests a view that nationalist parties can have both positive and negative impacts, possibly reflecting a variety of policies promoted by these parties and how these are perceived by different segments of the population. A minority of 6.7% of respondents believe that nationalist parties do not have a significant impact on democracy. This could reflect a perception that these parties are marginal or that their impact is negligible in the wider context of national or European politics. A small fraction, 8.1% of participants, see the impact of nationalist parties as positive on democracy. This indicates the existence of a niche of respondents who can appreciate the values or policies promoted by these parties, seeing them as a factor strengthening democracy.

Chi-Square test results reveal important information about how socio-demographic variables influence students' perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on democracy in the European Union. First, the age of students plays a significant role in how they perceive the influence of nationalist parties. This suggests that the experiences and perspectives of young people vary considerably depending on the life stage they are in, affecting how they interpret the role and impact of nationalist parties on democracy. Gender is another variable with a strong influence on political perceptions. This indicates significant differences between men and women in their perceptions of nationalist parties. This difference can be attributed to different social roles and life experiences, which shape each gender's political views.

On the other hand, residence environment does not show a statistically significant association. This suggests that students' perceptions of nationalist parties do not differ considerably between those living in urban and rural areas. This result could reflect a uniformity in information exposure and political opinion formation, regardless of residence. The educational level has a significant impact on perceptions. Students with different levels of education perceive the influence of nationalist parties differently, which can be explained by the fact that higher education tends to provide a more critical and informed perspective on political and social issues. Marital status is also significantly associated with perceptions of the influence of nationalist parties. This suggests that personal experiences of marital status influence how individuals perceive nationalist parties and their impact on democracy.

Students' monthly income significantly influences their perceptions. This shows that there are significant differences in perceptions of the influence of nationalist parties by income level. Students with different incomes have distinct perceptions, which can be attributed to varied economic experiences and concerns. Finally, students' socio-professional status significantly influences their perceptions. This indicates that experiences and positions occupied in professional life shape views on nationalist parties, reflecting the diversity of perspectives according to professional involvement and responsibilities.

Table 4 analyzes students' perceptions of three critical issues associated with nationalist parties in the European political context. Scores on a scale of 1 to 5 reflect students' level of satisfaction with the fulfillment of campaign promises, their level of awareness of the impact of nationalist parties on democracy, and their perception of the importance of participating in the European Parliamentary elections.

The first aspect examined is the fulfillment of the campaign promises of the nationalist parties, where a predominantly negative perception is observed. With a mean of 2.48 and a standard deviation of 1.12, the scores reflect a general disappointment with the ability of these parties to deliver on their

pledges. This feeling of uncertainty about policy promises can be attributed to possible discrepancies between electoral rhetoric and actual post-election actions. In terms of students' level of awareness of the impact of nationalist parties on European democracy, the data indicate moderate awareness, with a mean of 2.49 and a standard deviation of 1.19. This suggests that while students are aware of the presence and activity of nationalist parties, there is variation in how well they understand their profound impact on the political and social structure of the European Union. The third aspect analyzed, the importance of participating in the European Parliament elections, is rated much more positively. With a mean of 3.96 and a standard deviation of 1.12, the responses underline a broad recognition of the essential role that voting plays in maintaining and strengthening the democratic foundations of the Union. This consensus reflects a robust understanding of the importance of civic engagement in democratic processes, underlining a strong appreciation for the mechanisms for participation and influencing decisions at European level.

Table 4. Perceptions of promise fulfillment and political participation in the context of European nationalist parties.

Perceptions	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
Fulfilling the campaign promises of nationalist parties	2.48	1.12	2
Students' level of awareness of the impact of nationalist parties on European democracy	2.49	1.19	2
Participation in the European Parliament elections is important for maintaining democracy in the European Union	3.96	1.12	4

Variable	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient - beta	95% confidence interval for beta
<i>DV: Fulfilling the campaign promises of nationalist parties</i>				
Constant	2.358	.123	---	2.117 – 2.598
Graduated studies	.188	.056	.174	0.077 – 0.299
Income	-.151	.057	-.138	-0.264 – -0.039
<i>DV: Students' level of awareness of the impact of nationalist parties on European democracy</i>				
Constant	2.188	.121	---	1.951 – 2.426
Graduated studies	.161	.056	.139	0.051 – 0.272
<i>DV: Participation in the European Parliament elections is important to maintain democracy in the EU</i>				
Constant	4.341	0.175	---	3.997 – 4.685
Gender		0.110	-0.112	-0.467 – -0.036

Note: DV = dependent variable.

The results obtained from the multiple linear regression analysis provide a detailed insight into how various demographic and socio-economic characteristics influence perceptions of nationalist parties' compliance with campaign promises. First, the level of education of individuals plays a significant role. The data show that the level of education has a significant positive impact on the perception of fulfillment of campaign promises of nationalist parties. The unadjusted coefficient for the variable "completed education" is .188, with significance level $p=0.001$. This result suggests that as the level of education of the individual increases, the belief that nationalist parties fulfill their pledges also increases. The 95% confidence interval for this coefficient ranges from .077 to .299, reinforcing the relevance of education in the model. In contrast, the respondents' monthly income has a significant negative impact on the perception of nationalist parties' commitment compliance. The unadjusted

coefficient is $-.151$, with significance level $p=0.008$. These data indicate that as monthly income increases, the belief that nationalist parties fulfill their campaign promises decreases. The 95% confidence interval for this coefficient ranges between $-.264$ and $-.039$, emphasizing the strength of this negative relationship.

In terms of students' level of awareness of the impact of nationalist parties on European democracy, educational attainment is again found to be a significant factor. The coefficient for the variable "graduate education" is $.161$, with a significance level $p=0.004$, suggesting that a higher level of education is associated with a better perception of students' information. The confidence interval for this coefficient ranges from $.051$ to $.272$.

Gender also plays a significant role in the perception of the importance of participating in the European Parliamentary elections for maintaining democracy in the European Union. The coefficient for gender is $-.112$, with a significance level $p=0.022$. This result indicates that there is a significant difference between men and women in the perception of the importance of participation in the European Parliamentary elections, with women being more skeptical. The confidence interval for this coefficient is between $-.467$ and $-.036$, emphasizing the statistical significance of this variable.

Table 5 explores students' understanding and concerns about the various perceived threats to European democracy, providing a comprehensive perspective on the degree of alarm that young people feel about these challenges. The results are expressed in a series of means, standard deviations and medians for each identified threat, thus providing a detailed picture of students' feelings.

A significant result reflects the increasing concern about populism and nationalism, with a mean of 3.39 and a relatively low standard deviation. This reflects moderate to high concern, highlighting the frictions between nationalist tendencies and social and political cohesion in the European context. Disinformation and cyber-attacks are also major sources of concern, with a mean of 3.80 and a median of 4 , indicating a keen awareness of the risks these phenomena pose to the integrity of democratic processes. This score clearly shows that students are deeply concerned about the ability of disinformation to distort the truth and the potentially devastating impact of cyber-attacks on national security. Political and social polarization, with a mean of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 1.03 , is perceived as a factor aggravating existing cleavages and threatening democratic dialogue. This emphasizes the need for effective strategies to promote unity and dialogue in a fragmented political landscape. In addition, the erosion of trust in democratic institutions, which scored an average of 3.70 , is seen as an indicator of the vulnerability of democracy. This score reflects the perception that democratic institutions, which are the backbone of governance in the EU, need to be robust and immune to external influences or corruption to ensure the effective functioning of society.

Also, external influence and interference in electoral processes, with an average of 3.52 , are considered as serious threats, revealing fears about the ability of external actors to influence electoral results and, therefore, the political direction of the European Union. One of the significant issues highlighted by student responses relates to the restriction of press freedom and freedom of expression, with a mean of 3.47 and a standard deviation of 1.10 . These scores emphasize a moderate to high concern about the potential negative effects on government transparency and accountability. This score reflects concerns about possible limitations imposed on journalists and the media, which could inhibit society's ability to stay informed and monitor government actions. Rising economic and social inequality, with a mean of 3.69 and a standard deviation of 1.05 , is perceived as a serious threat to social cohesion and political stability. These figures indicate a recognition of the negative impact that inequalities can have on social solidarity and social integration, amplifying existing divisions and fueling civic discontent.

Table 5. Perceptions of the main threats to European democracy today.

Main threats to European democracy	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
Populism and nationalism on the rise	3.39	1.07	3
Misinformation and cyber attacks	3.80	1.04	4
Political and social polarization	3.57	1.03	4
Eroding trust in democratic institutions	3.70	1.02	4
External influence / foreign interference in electoral processes	3.52	1.00	3
Restricting freedom of the press and freedom of expression	3.47	1.10	3
Rising economic and social inequalities	3.69	1.05	4
Climate change and environmental crises	3.43	1.16	3
Weakening international cooperation and multilateralism	3.59	1.01	4

Variable	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient - beta	95% confidence interval for beta
<i>DV: Populism and nationalism on the rise</i>				
Constant	3.804	.167		3.477 – 4.131
Gender	-.274	.104	-.128	-0.478 – -0.070
<i>DV: Misinformation and cyberattacks</i>				
Constant	4.139	.163		3.819 – 4.458
Gender	-.223	.102	-.107	-0.423 – -0.022
<i>DV: Political and social polarization</i>				
Constant	4.252	.277		3.707 – 4.797
Gender	-.341	.105	-.165	-0.547 – -0.134
Residence	-.213	.113	-.092	-0.434 – 0.009
Graduated studies	.174	.056	.174	0.064 – 0.284
Income	-.148	.051	-.146	-0.249 – -0.047
<i>DV: Eroding trust in democratic institutions</i>				
Constant	3.889	.179		3.537 – 4.240
Gender	-.226	.100	-.110	-0.422 – -0.030
Income	.100	.049	.100	0.004 – 0.197
<i>DV: External influence and foreign interference in electoral processes</i>				
Constant	4.143	.264		3.625 – 4.661
Age	.190	.065	.146	0.064 – 0.317
Gender	-.392	.098	-.194	-0.584 – -0.199
Residence	-.283	.108	-.125	-0.495 – -0.072
<i>DV: Restricting press freedom and freedom of expression</i>				
Constant	4.073	.170		3.739 – 4.407
Gender	-.394	.106	-.179	-0.604 – -0.185
<i>DV: Growing economic and social inequalities</i>				
Constant	3.302	.188		2.932 – 3.673
Marital status	.508	.173	.152	0.168 – 0.848
Income	-.118	.053	-.114	-0.222 – -0.013
Graduated studies	3.302	.188		
<i>DV: Climate change and environmental crises</i>				
Constant	3.497	.127		3.246 – 3.747
Graduated studies	.114	.059	.101	-0.002 – 0.229
Income	-.182	.060	-.160	-0.299 – -0.065
<i>DV: Weakening international cooperation and multilateralism</i>				
Constant	3.970	.150		3.676 – 4.265
Residence	-.299	.111	-.131	-0.518 – -0.081

Note: DV = dependent variable.

In addition, climate change and environmental crises, with a mean of 3.43 and a standard deviation of 1.16, are identified as major risk factors for environmental sustainability and, indirectly,

for long-term social and economic stability. This score reflects students' deep concern about the need for effective and coordinated action in environmental policies to counter the effects of environmental adversities. The weakening of international cooperation and multilateralism, with a mean of 3.59 and a standard deviation of 1.01, is perceived as a worrying trend that could undermine collective efforts to respond to global challenges. The score indicates an awareness of the importance of international solidarity in effectively managing transnational crises and promoting peace and shared prosperity.

Multiple linear regression analysis investigates the influence of independent variables (IV) on dependent variables (DV) that represent the main threats to European democracy today. The results are presented for each dependent variable, providing a detailed insight into the significant influences identified. Growing populism and nationalism is one of the main threats analyzed. The results indicate that gender has a negative and significant influence on this dependent variable, with an unadjusted coefficient of -0.274 and significance $p < 0.009$, suggesting that women perceive less populism and rising nationalism compared to men. For misinformation and cyber-attacks, gender also negatively and significantly influences this dependent variable, with an unadjusted coefficient of -0.223 and significance $p < 0.029$. This indicates a different perception of misinformation and cyber-attacks by gender. The analysis of political and social polarization revealed that gender has a negative and significant effect, while residence has a negative but insignificant effect. Educational level and monthly income show significant influences, with coefficients of 0.174 and -0.148.

In terms of the erosion of trust in democratic institutions, gender has a negative and significant effect and monthly income has a positive and significant effect, suggesting that people with higher income have more trust in democratic institutions. External influence and foreign interference in electoral processes is positively and significantly influenced by age and negatively and significantly influenced by gender and residence. For the restriction of press freedom and freedom of expression, gender has a negative and significant influence, indicating a different perception of this threat by gender. The analysis of the increase in economic and social inequality shows that marital status positively and significantly influences this dependent variable, while monthly income has a negative and significant effect. Climate change and environmental crises are positively but insignificantly affected by educational attainment and negatively and significantly affected by monthly income. Finally, the weakening of international cooperation and multilateralism is negatively and significantly influenced by residence.

With respect to students' perceptions of the representation of nationalist parties in the media, about half of the respondents (46.2%) perceive the portrayal of nationalist parties in the media as predominantly negative. This suggests a widespread critical view of nationalist parties, possibly due to their perceived divisive controversies or politics. A smaller fraction of the sample (11.5%) perceives the representation of these parties in the media as predominantly positive. This segment could reflect an alignment of respondents' political views with those of nationalist parties or an appreciation of their actions. A quarter of the respondents (24.7%) see the portrayal of nationalist parties in the media as balanced, indicating that the coverage gives a relatively neutral picture or a combination of positive and negative perspectives. 17.5% of respondents believe that nationalist parties are not significantly represented in the media. This view may suggest that these parties are marginalized in the media discourse or are not perceived as relevant in the current political landscape.

Table 6 explores students' perceptions of the aims of nationalist parties in the European Parliament. The data are presented as scores on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 indicates an extremely negative perception and 5 an extremely positive one. Mean scores, standard deviations and medians are calculated for each objective.

Table 6. Perceptions on the objectives of nationalist parties in the European Parliament.

Main threats to European democracy	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
Degree of transparency	2.37	1.07	2
Protecting national sovereignty	3.40	1.12	3
Promoting national economic interests	3.38	1.09	3
Representing young people's interests in the EU	2.94	1.29	3
The end of the European Union	3.01	1.36	3
Protecting national interests in a globalizing world	3.31	1.07	3
Make peace with the Russian Federation	3.26	1.24	3
To eliminate NATO from the European scene	2.82	1.37	3

Variable	Unstandardized coefficient	Standard error	Standardized coefficient - beta	95% confidence interval for beta
<i>DV: Degree of transparency</i>				
Constant	1.781	0.251		1.287 – 2.275
Age	-0.410	0.080	-0.295	-0.568 – -0.253
Residence	0.282	0.116	0.117	0.055 – 0.509
Marital status	0.643	0.182	0.188	0.286 – 1.001
Income	0.152	0.057	0.145	0.040 – 0.264
<i>DV: Promoting national economic interests</i>				
Constant	3.389	0.314		2.772 – 4.007
Age	-0.308	0.100	-0.216	-0.504 – -0.111
Gender	-0.260	0.113	-0.118	-0.483 – -0.037
Residence	0.234	0.122	0.095	-0.006 – 0.474
Graduated studies	0.179	0.076	0.169	0.030 – 0.327
Status	0.159	0.061	0.160	0.040 – 0.278
<i>DV: Representing young people's interests in the EU</i>				
Constant	1.882	0.254		1.383 – 2.380
Residence	0.287	0.140	0.098	0.011 – 0.562
Graduated studies	0.263	0.074	0.210	0.118 – 0.409
Status	0.252	0.065	0.214	0.123 – 0.380
Income	-0.161	0.063	-0.127	-0.286 – -0.036
<i>DV: Abolition of the European Union</i>				
Constant	3.591	0.341		2.921 – 4.262
Gender	-0.531	0.135	-0.194	-0.797 – -0.265
Graduated studies	0.166	0.076	0.126	0.017 – 0.315
Marital status	-0.436	0.207	-0.100	-0.843 – -0.028
Status	0.219	0.069	0.177	0.083 – 0.355
<i>DV: Protecting national interests in the context of globalization</i>				
Constant	3.530	0.208		3.121 – 3.940
Gender	-0.335	0.106	-0.156	-0.543 – -0.126
Status	0.158	0.048	0.163	0.064 – 0.253
<i>DV: Make peace with the Russian Federation</i>				
Constant	4.413	0.302		3.819 – 5.008
Gender	-0.541	0.122	-0.217	-0.781 – -0.301
Marital status	-0.375	0.203	-0.094	-0.774 – 0.024
Status	0.139	0.058	0.123	0.025 – 0.253
Income	-0.111	0.062	-0.091	-0.232 – 0.011
<i>DV: Eliminate NATO from the European scene</i>				
Constant	3.202	0.319		2.574 – 3.930
Age	0.280	0.114	0.157	0.056 – 0.504
Gender	-0.418	0.129	-0.152	-0.672 – -0.165
Marital status	-0.385	0.220	-0.088	-0.817 – 0.047
Status	0.370	0.068	0.296	0.236 – 0.504
Income	-0.309	0.069	-0.229	-0.445 – -0.174

The degree of transparency has a mean of 2.37 and a standard deviation of 1.07, with the median standing at 2. This below-average score suggests a perceived lack of transparency in the activities of nationalist parties, which could raise concerns about the way in which they conduct their operations. Protecting national sovereignty gets a mean of 3.40, a standard deviation of 1.12 and a median of 3. This is one of the higher scores, indicating a relative appreciation for nationalist parties' efforts to protect national sovereignty. Promoting national economic interests has a mean of 3.38 and a standard deviation of 1.09, with a median of 3. This reflects a positive perception, like that for protecting sovereignty, underlining a value respondents place on protecting national economic interests. Representation of youth interests in the EU has a mean of 2.94 and a standard deviation of 1.29, with a median of 3. The scores indicate a mixed perception, possibly due to variations in nationalist parties' youth-related policies. The dissolution of the European Union receives a mean score of 3.01 and a standard deviation of 1.36, with a median of 3. This is a controversial topic, and averages close to the center of the scale reflect the division of public opinion. Protecting national interests in the context of globalization has a mean of 3.31 and a standard deviation of 1.07, with a median of 3. This suggests a moderate rating for efforts to protect national interests in the face of the challenges of globalization. Peace with the Russian Federation and the elimination of NATO from the European scene have averages of 3.26 and 2.82 respectively, with standard deviations of 1.24 and 1.37 respectively. These scores reflect divergent attitudes, indicating polarization and controversy among respondents on these foreign policy issues.

The multiple linear regression analysis performed revealed the relationships between the independent variables (IV) and the dependent variables (DV) for various political and economic objectives. The results are detailed below for each dependent variable, providing insight into the significant influences identified.

The degree of transparency is the first dependent variable analyzed. We found that the age of respondents negatively influences the degree of transparency, with an unadjusted coefficient of -0.410 and significance $p < 0.001$, indicating a significant negative relationship. In contrast, residence has a positive and significant effect. Also, marital status and monthly income positively and significantly influence the degree of transparency, with unadjusted coefficients of 0.643 and 0.152 respectively ($p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.008$). In terms of promoting national economic interests, age negatively influences this objective. Respondents' gender also has a significant negative effect. Residence, although showing a positive effect, is not significant. On the other hand, educational attainment and socio-professional status have positive and significant effects on the promotion of national economic interests, with unadjusted coefficients of 0.179 and 0.159 respectively ($p < 0.019$ and $p < 0.009$).

In the analysis of the representation of young people's interests in the EU, we observed that domicile positively and significantly influences this dependent variable. Educational attainment and socio-professional status also have significant positive effects, with coefficients of 0.263 and 0.252 ($p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.000$). In contrast, monthly income has a negative and significant effect on the representation of young people's interests. For the dissolution of the European Union, the respondents' gender has a negative and significant influence on this dependent variable. Educational attainment has a significant positive effect, while marital status has a significant negative effect. Socio-professional status positively and significantly influences the dissolution of the EU. In the context of protecting national interests in the context of globalization, respondents' gender has a negative and significant effect. Socio-professional status positively and significantly influences the protection of national interests, with an unadjusted coefficient of 0.158 ($p < 0.001$).

For the goal of making peace with the Russian Federation, gender negatively and significantly influences this goal (unadjusted coefficient of -0.541, $p < 0.001$). Marital status, although negative, is not significant. In contrast, socio-professional status has a positive and significant effect, and monthly income has a negative insignificant effect. Finally, the analysis of the dependent variable related to the elimination of NATO from the European scene reveals that age has a positive and significant influence on this objective, gender has a significant negative effect, marital status has a non-significant negative effect. Socio-professional status has a positive and significant effect on NATO attrition, while monthly income has a negative and significant effect.

Table 7. Perceptions of strategies to strengthen democratic structures in the European context.

Main strategies	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
Strengthening citizens' civic education and understanding of democratic principles	3.81	1.10	4
Promoting active participation of citizens in political and decision-making processes	3.88	1.05	4
Strengthening transparency and accountability in political and government institutions	3.90	1.09	4
Better regulation to combat disinformation and fake news	3.89	1.12	4
Support press freedom and protect journalists from intimidation and censorship	3.82	1.07	4
Stimulating intercultural dialog and mutual understanding between diverse communities	3.78	1.10	4
Increased support for civil society organizations promoting democracy and human rights	3.86	1.06	4
Encouraging international cooperation to counter external interference in democratic processes	3.86	1.03	4
Developing secure digital platforms to encourage participation and civic engagement	3.81	1.06	4
Implement fair economic and social policies to reduce inequalities and prevent polarization	3.89	1.05	4

Analyzing the data in Table 7 gives us a detailed insight into how young people perceive the different strategies aimed at strengthening democratic structures in the European context. We observe a variety of reactions, reflected in mean values and standard deviations, which indicate the degree of consensus or diversity of opinions among respondents.

Civic understanding and education are seen as essential, with a mean of 3.81 and a standard deviation of 1.10. This suggests widespread recognition of the importance of a solid knowledge base of democratic principles, although the relative variation indicates differences in perceptions of the effectiveness of current civic education. Promoting active participation in political processes has an impressive mean of 3.88, with a standard deviation of 1.05, reflecting a strong consensus among young people about the crucial role of civic engagement in sustaining democracy. The moderate standard deviation shows that while majorities agree, there is variation in the intensity of beliefs. Increasing transparency in government institutions is also strongly supported, with a mean of 3.90 and a standard deviation of 1.09. This score indicates a strong desire to see more openness and accountability in government, with variation that may reflect different personal experiences with state institutions. Improving the rules to combat misinformation is critical, as shown by the mean of 3.89 and standard deviation of 1.12. Respondents are clearly concerned about the impact of false information, highlighting the need for effective measures to protect the integrity of the public information space.

Support for a free press receives a mean of 3.82 and a standard deviation of 1.07, highlighting the value young people place on a free press as a pillar of democracy, although the variance indicates that perceptions may vary due to differences in trust in the media. Stimulating intercultural dialogue has a mean of 3.78 and a standard deviation of 1.10, reflecting the recognition of the need to promote understanding and respect between the diverse cultural communities in Europe, with some discrepancies that might suggest different levels of exposure to diversity. The increase in support for civil society organizations, with a mean of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 1.06, indicates an appreciation of their role in promoting and defending civil rights, with some variation in opinions that may reflect varying degrees of direct interaction with such organizations. Encouraging international cooperation has a mean score of 3.86 and a standard deviation of 1.03, indicating a positive view of the importance of transnational solidarity in countering external threats to democracy, with variations that may suggest different perspectives on the effectiveness of these efforts. The development of digital platforms for civic participation has a mean of 3.81 and a standard deviation of 1.06, showing an acceptance of technology to improve civic engagement, but with variations showing that there are still uncertainties about their implementation and accessibility. Finally, the implementation of economically and socially equitable policies is rated with a mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 1.05, highlighting a broad recognition of the need to reduce inequalities to prevent polarization, with variation indicating different views on the most effective strategies to mitigate these inequalities.

Table 8. Perceptions of the foundations of European democracy.

The foundation of European democracy	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
The rule of law	3.88	1.02	4
Human rights and fundamental freedoms	4.18	.99	4
Political pluralism	3.79	1.09	4
Separation of state powers	3.99	1.03	4
The principle of sovereignty of the people	3.94	1.06	4
Equality before the law	4.06	1.05	4
Freedom of the press and freedom of expression	3.95	1.05	4
Government transparency and accountability	3.99	1.05	4
Protection of minorities	3.79	1.08	4
Active civic and political participation	3.94	1.03	4

Students' perceptions of the fundamentals of European democracy are key to understanding how young people relate to democratic values and the institutions that support them. These perceptions can provide a detailed insight into the level of awareness and acceptance of democratic principles among the younger generation, who represent the political future of the European Union. The data presented in Table 8 reflect a comprehensive overview of students' perceptions of the fundamentals of European democracy, revealing varying levels of acceptance and awareness of key democratic principles.

With a mean of 3.88 and a standard deviation of 1.02, students recognize the importance of the rule of law in maintaining a functioning democracy. The median value of 4 indicates that many respondents consider this principle to be essential, but the relative variation in responses suggests that there is a segment of students who may be less aware or more skeptical of its consistent application. Human rights and fundamental freedoms is the highest rated principle, with a mean of 4.18 and a standard deviation of 0.99, indicating a high

level of agreement among students on the importance of human rights and fundamental freedoms. The median of 4 underlines a strong consensus that these rights are pillars of democracy, essential to protect the individual from abuse. Political pluralism is rated with a mean of 3.79 and a standard deviation of 1.09. This reflects an overall positive assessment, but with greater variability in the responses, suggesting that some students may have reservations or negative experiences of political diversity. The median of 4 indicates that many respondents consider this principle important, but there are also divergent perceptions.

With a mean of 3.99 and a standard deviation of 1.03, the separation of powers in the state is well appreciated by students. The median value of 4 indicates that the majority consider this principle to be fundamental for preventing abuse of power and ensuring balanced and accountable governance. The principle of the sovereignty of the people has a mean of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 1.06, suggesting a generally positive assessment of the sovereignty of the people, with varied responses indicating differences in perceptions of the effectiveness of this principle in practice. The median of 4 reflects a broad acceptance of the idea that power should belong to the people. Rated with a mean of 4.06 and a standard deviation of 1.05, equality before the law is considered very important by students. The median of 4 underlines a general agreement that all citizens should be treated equally by the legal system without discrimination. With a mean of 3.95 and a standard deviation of 1.05, freedom of the press and freedom of expression is seen as essential for a healthy democracy. The median of 4 indicates a robust appreciation of this principle, with variations in responses suggesting differing perceptions of the degree of press freedom and accountability today.

Government transparency and accountability is rated with a mean of 3.99 and a standard deviation of 1.05, indicating a clear desire for transparency and accountability in government. The median of 4 indicates that most students consider these characteristics vital to public trust in democratic institutions. With a mean of 3.79 and a standard deviation of 1.08, the protection of minorities is an important principle for students, but with notable variability in responses. This may reflect differences in personal experiences and perceptions of how minorities are treated in different social and political contexts. Active civic and political participation has a mean of 3.94 and a standard deviation of 1.03, indicating a strong appreciation for the active involvement of citizens in political processes. The median of 4 suggests a consensus that civic participation is crucial for maintaining and strengthening democracy.

Discussion

Support for nationalist parties and democratic values. The analysis of hypothesis H1 highlights the correlation between support for nationalist parties and support for traditional democratic values, focusing on Romanian students (Doiciar and Crețan, 2021). The results presented in Table 1 and Table 2 provide a detailed picture of political perceptions and behaviors among different demographic groups. First, the data in Table 1 reveal significant variations in the level of trust in nationalist parties between different age groups. The 18-22 age group, with a mean of 2.55, indicates a moderate level of trust, suggesting a relative openness to these parties among young people (Armeanu and Feșnic, 2010; Wang, 2014). In contrast, the 28-32 age group shows the lowest trust, with an average of only

1.77, showing a pronounced aversion to nationalist parties. In addition to age, gender proves to be a determinant, with significant differences between men and women in terms of trust in nationalist parties (Chi-Square = 28.413, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that men are generally more likely to support nationalist parties than women (Fangen and Lichtenberg, 2021; Hartevelde et al., 2015; Spierings and Zaslove, 2015).

Interestingly, residency (urban vs. rural) almost reaches statistical significance ($p = 0.057$), indicating a possible trend of variation in trust in nationalist parties based on residency. Although not strong enough to be considered significant at the 0.05 level, this association suggests that political perceptions are also influenced by residential background, with a possible polarization between urban and rural (Mitsch, Lee, and Morrow, 2021; Rickardsson, 2021). Educational level and socio-professional status are key variables influencing trust in nationalist parties. Individuals with higher levels of education tend to have lower trust in these parties (Chi-Square = 44.639, $df = 20$, $p = 0.001$), likely reflecting a greater awareness of the political and ideological implications of nationalism. Also, significant socio-professional status (Chi-Square = 52.491, $df = 12$, $p < 0.001$) emphasizes the role of economic and professional background in shaping political views (Bekhuis, Lubbers, and Verkuyten, 2014; Hjerem, 2001; Savelkoul and Scheepers, 2016). Monthly income is another variable with significant influence, with higher income earners having lower trust in nationalist parties (Chi-Square = 28.987, $df = 16$, $p = 0.024$). This may reflect economic stability and differing perspectives on the need for radical policy changes promoted by nationalist parties (Han, 2016).

Table 2 provides valuable information about young people's perceptions of the undermining of democracy by nationalist parties. The mean score of 3.54, with a standard deviation of 1.10, shows a moderately negative view, indicating that although there are concerns, these are not perceived as extremely serious by all respondents. The variety of opinions, as evidenced by the standard deviation, reflects the diversity of students' experiences and perceptions, influenced by personal and educational factors (Mycock and Tonge, 2012; Pollock, Brock, and Ellison, 2015; Ellison, Pollock, and Grimm, 2020). Multiple regression analysis reveals that age has a positive and significant influence on the perception of undermining democracy (unadjusted coefficient = 0.527, $p < 0.001$). Thus, older students tend to see nationalist parties as a greater threat to democracy. In contrast, marital status and income have negative and significant influences, suggesting that people who are married or have higher incomes are less concerned about the impact of nationalist parties on democracy.

The data reveal complex correlations between support for nationalist parties and support for democratic values. Age, gender, level of education, socio-professional status and income are determinants that shape these perceptions. Although young people recognize some degree of undermining of democracy by nationalist parties, opinions vary significantly, reflecting the diversity of personal experiences and contexts. These findings underscore the need for continued critical discussion and analysis to better understand the complex dynamics of nationalist politics in democratic contexts (Zhong and Hwang, 2020; Loewen, Heroux-Legault, and Miguel, 2015; Halikiopoulou, Mock, and Vasilopoulou, 2013).

Based on the results obtained and analyzed, hypothesis H1, which postulates the existence of a significant correlation between support for nationalist parties and support for traditional democratic values among Romanian students, can be partially validated. The data reveal significant associations between socio-demographic variables, such as age, gender, education level and socio-professional status, and the level of trust in nationalist parties, suggesting that there are demographic factors that influence political perceptions. However, the diversity of opinions and significant variations in the data collected indicate that support for nationalist parties is not a univocal predictor of support for

traditional democratic values. Thus, the hypothesis is validated to the extent that it highlights correlations between the variables studied but is limited by the complexity and variability of the socio-political context among students.

Impact of educational level on perceptions. Analyzing the collected data and related results, it can be observed that negative perceptions of nationalist parties and their impact on democracy are more pronounced among students with a university level of education compared to those with a pre-university level. This differentiation can be attributed to different levels of political information and awareness influenced by higher education, which tends to provide a more critical perspective on political phenomena.

The results in Table 3 indicate that 34.7% of respondents believe that nationalist parties undermine democracy, while 50.3% identify a mixed impact, and only 6.7% believe that these parties have no significant impact. These data reflect significant concerns about the destabilizing influence of nationalist parties on democracy, particularly among those with a university education (Jafarova, 2022). Chi-Square analysis reveals significant associations between socio-demographic variables and perceptions of nationalist parties. Age and gender play an important role, with Chi-Square values of 46.612 and 35.045 respectively, both with p-values of 0.000. This suggests that young men and women perceive the impact of nationalist parties on democracy differently, influenced by their experiences and social roles (Deckman and Cassese, 2019; Binkowska-Bury et al., 2010).

Interestingly, residential background does not show a significant association (Chi-Square = 3.005, p-value = 0.391), indicating that perceptions of nationalist parties do not vary considerably between urban and rural students. This could reflect a uniformity in information exposure and political opinion formation, regardless of residential background. Education level is found to have a significant impact on perceptions, with a Chi-Square of 43.374 and a p-value of 0.000. University-educated students tend to perceive nationalist parties as more detrimental to democracy compared to pre-university students. This can be explained by the fact that higher education favors the development of critical thinking and complex analysis of the political context (Peptan, Holt, and Mărcău, 2023). Marital status and monthly income significantly influence perceptions of nationalist parties (Chi-Square of 36.992 and 42.063, respectively, both with p-values of 0.000). Married or higher-income respondents are less likely to see nationalist parties as a major threat to democracy than are unmarried or lower-income respondents (McKenna, 2016).

Table 4 provides additional insight into students' perceptions of the fulfillment of nationalist parties' campaign promises and the level of awareness of their impact. The meaning of 2.48 for fulfillment of promises indicates a predominantly negative perception, suggesting disappointment with the ability of these parties to deliver on their pledges. In addition, the mean of 2.49 for the level of information indicates that students are only moderately informed about the impact of nationalist parties, highlighting the need for more in-depth political education (Peptan, 2019; Peptan, Holt, and Mărcău, 2023). In terms of the importance of participation in the European Parliamentary elections, the average of 3.96 reflects a clear recognition of the essential role of civic participation in maintaining democracy. This underlines young people's awareness of the importance of active political involvement in strengthening democratic structures (Brooks, 2009; Barros, Monteiro, and Leite, 2022).

Multiple regression analysis indicates that educational attainment significantly influences students' perceptions of campaign promise fulfillment and the importance of participating in elections. The positive coefficient for graduate education (0.188) suggests that higher education is associated with more favorable perceptions of pledge fulfillment, while the negative coefficient for income (-0.151) indicates an inverse relationship between income and perceptions of pledge fulfillment.

Hypothesis H2 is thus validated by the results, showing that negative perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on democracy are more pronounced among university students. This emphasizes the crucial role of education in shaping political perceptions and the importance of accurate and complete information for responsible civic participation.

The influence of socio-demographic factors on perceptions. Analyzing the hypothesis H3, which suggests that socio-demographic factors such as age, gender and residential background significantly influence students' attitudes towards nationalist parties and their perception of their long-term impact on democracy, the results largely confirm this hypothesis. **Table 5** details students' perceptions of the main threats to European democracy, highlighting how these socio-demographic factors influence perceptions. Rising populism and nationalism are perceived as significant threats, with a mean of 3.39 and a standard deviation of 1.07. Gender plays a key role here, with women perceiving rising populism and nationalism as less threatening than men (Spierings and Zaslove, 2017; Mărcău, Peptan, and Preda, 2023).

Misinformation and cyber-attacks are other major sources of concern, with a mean of 3.80 and a median of 4. These phenomena are perceived differently by gender, with an unadjusted coefficient of -0.223 and a significance $p = 0.029$, suggesting that women are less concerned about these threats compared to men (Almenar et al., 2021). Political and social polarization is another important threat, with a mean of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 1.03. The analysis shows that gender and residence have significant influences on this perception, with unadjusted coefficients of -0.341 ($p = 0.001$) and -0.213 ($p = 0.059$) respectively, indicating significant differences between men and women, but also notable variation between urban and rural areas (Ondercin and Lizotte, 2020; Antinyan et al., 2021).

Trust in democratic institutions is eroded, with a mean of 3.70, and this perception is influenced by gender (unadjusted coefficient of -0.226, $p = 0.024$) and income (unadjusted coefficient of 0.100, $p = 0.040$). This suggests that people with higher incomes have greater trust in democratic institutions, while women perceive a more pronounced erosion of this trust. External influence and foreign interference in electoral processes are considered serious threats, with a mean of 3.52. Age and gender influence these perceptions, with unadjusted coefficients of 0.190 ($p = 0.003$) and -0.392 ($p = 0.000$) respectively. Young men and women perceive these threats differently, emphasizing the importance of life experiences and socio-cultural context in shaping political views (Mohan and Wall, 2019; Tomz and Weeks, 2020).

Restriction of press freedom and freedom of expression is perceived as a moderate to high threat, with a mean of 3.47 and a standard deviation of 1.10. Gender has a significant influence on this perception (unadjusted coefficient of -0.394, $p = 0.000$), indicating that women are less concerned than men about the restriction of fundamental freedoms (Voronova, 2015). Increasing economic and social inequality, with a mean of 3.69, reflects serious concern, influenced by marital status (unadjusted coefficient of 0.508, $p = 0.004$) and income (unadjusted coefficient of -0.118, $p = 0.028$). Unmarried and lower income individuals are more concerned about these inequalities, highlighting the impact of social and economic status on political perceptions (Roex, Huijts, and Sieben, 2019).

Climate change and environmental crises, with a mean of 3.43, are identified as major risk factors, influenced by educational attainment (unadjusted coefficient of 0.114, $p = 0.053$) and income (unadjusted coefficient of -0.182, $p = 0.002$). This suggests that higher education contributes to a better understanding of the impacts of climate change, while higher income may reduce the perception of risk associated with climate change (Selm et al., 2019; Mărcău et al., 2022). Weakening international cooperation and multilateralism is perceived as a threat, with a mean of 3.59 and a

standard deviation of 1.01. Domicile significantly influences this perception (unadjusted coefficient of -0.299, $p = 0.007$), indicating a variation by residence. The portrayal of nationalist parties in the media is seen as predominantly negative by 46.2% of respondents, reflecting a critical perception of these parties. This suggests that nationalist parties are often presented in an unfavorable light, contributing to a controversial public image (Faude and Parizek, 2020).

In conclusion, Hypothesis H3 is validated, showing that socio-demographic factors such as age, gender and residential background significantly influence students' attitudes towards nationalist parties and perceptions of their long-term impact on democracy. These results underline the complexity of the interactions between demographic characteristics and political perceptions, the need for a nuanced approach in analyzing students' views, and the importance of tailored educational and information policies to address the diversity of these perceptions.

The role of adequate information in forming political opinion. Analyzing hypothesis H4, that adequate information about policies and their consequences reduces support for nationalist parties, the results presented in Table 6 and Table 7 suggest that access to quality and credible information plays a crucial role in shaping students' political opinion.

The data in Table 6 show students' perceptions of the aims of nationalist parties in the European Parliament. The degree of transparency of these parties receives a low mean of 2.37, reflecting a general perception of a lack of transparency. This lack of transparency may fuel mistrust and reduce support for nationalist parties, highlighting the importance of adequate information (Nahtigal, 2018). Protecting national sovereignty and promoting national economic interests are perceived more positively, with averages of 3.40 and 3.38. These scores reflect a moderate appreciation for these objectives, indicating that while there is support for protecting sovereignty and economic interests, it is not strong enough to counteract the negative effects of poor information (Vila Maior, 2019).

Representation of young people's interests in the EU receives a mixed score, with a mean of 2.94, indicating variations in perceptions. This suggests that adequate information can positively or negatively influence support for nationalist parties depending on the specific policies and how they are communicated to the public (Fomina, 2017). The more controversial goals, such as disbanding the European Union and removing NATO from the European scene, have average scores of 3.01 and 2.82, reflecting polarized opinions. This polarization indicates that access to detailed and balanced information can help form a more nuanced political opinion, reducing support for extreme measures promoted by nationalist parties (Gizicki, 2019; Peptan, 2022).

Table 7 explores the strategies perceived as essential for strengthening democratic structures in the European context. Strengthening civic education and understanding of democratic principles is rated with an average of 3.81, suggesting recognition of the importance of education for building informed and involved citizens. Promoting the active participation of citizens in political and decision-making processes, with an average of 3.88, underlines the crucial role of civic engagement in sustaining democracy (Abendschon, Kleer, and Faas, 2022; Blasko, Costa, and Toscano, 2018). Strengthening transparency and accountability in political and government institutions is strongly supported, with an average of 3.90, indicating a desire to see open and accountable government. Improving regulations to combat disinformation and fake news (Peptan and Mărcău, 2024), rated at 3.89, reflects a concern for protecting the integrity of public information, which is essential for the formation of fair political opinions (Saurwein and Spencer-Smith, 2020; Mișcoiu, Pantea, and Petrila, 2023).

Supporting press freedom and protecting journalists from intimidation and censorship, with an average of 3.82, and fostering intercultural dialogue, with an average of 3.78, highlight the need to

protect fundamental rights and promote understanding between diverse communities. Increased support for civil society organizations, with an average of 3.86, underlines the appreciation for the role of these organizations in promoting democracy and human rights (Dutta and Williamson, 2016; Oji, Adibe, and Okorie, 2022). Encouraging international cooperation and the development of secure digital platforms for civic participation, both with averages of 3.86 and 3.81, reflect recognition of the importance of international collaboration and technology for civic engagement. Implementing equitable economic and social policies, rated at 3.89, indicates the need to address inequalities to prevent polarization and sustain democracy (Saurwein and Spencer-Smith, 2020; Brihan and Petrilă, 2025).

Hypothesis H4 is validated by the results, highlighting that access to quality and credible information plays a crucial role in reducing support for nationalist parties and in forming informed political opinions. Education, transparency, accountability and combating misinformation are essential for strengthening democracy and creating a healthy and balanced political climate

Public policies

Public policies need to be built on a deep understanding of the factors that influence young people's political perceptions and behavior. By promoting civic education, enhancing transparency, fighting misinformation, stimulating civic participation, reducing inequalities and supporting intercultural dialog, a healthy and balanced political environment can be created.

One of the most important aspects identified in our analysis is the role of education in shaping political opinion. The results showed that students with higher levels of education tend to have more critical perceptions of nationalist parties and are more aware of the importance of democratic values. Thus, effective public policy should include robust educational programs that promote understanding of democratic principles, the rule of law and human rights. These programs should be integrated into school and university curricula and supported by extracurricular activities and information campaigns.

The results highlighted the need for transparency and accountability in political and governmental institutions to strengthen public trust in democracy. Public policy should focus on creating independent oversight and audit mechanisms to ensure that government processes are open and accountable. Laws should also be promoted to facilitate citizens' access to information of public interest and protect the right to information.

Combating misinformation and protecting media freedom are essential for maintaining an informed public space and preventing the harmful influences of nationalist parties. Public policies must include strict regulations for digital and media platforms to combat the spread of fake news and disinformation. At the same time, it is crucial to protect journalists from intimidation and censorship, ensuring that they can operate in a free and safe environment.

Active participation of citizens in political processes is vital for a healthy democracy. Public policies should facilitate citizens' access to decision-making processes by developing secure digital platforms that encourage civic participation and political engagement. Initiatives should also be promoted to encourage the involvement of young people in political life, including through volunteer programs, government internships and youth councils.

Rising economic and social inequality is perceived as a major threat to social cohesion and political stability. Public policies should focus on the implementation of equitable economic and social measures that reduce polarization and promote social inclusion. These measures can include income redistribution policies, equal access to education and health, and support programs for disadvantaged communities.

Research limitation

Our study, while providing a valuable insight into Romanian students' perceptions of the impact of nationalist parties on democracy, has some limitations that need to be considered when interpreting the results. One of the main limitations of this research is related to sampling. Although we managed to collect data from 417 students, the sample cannot be considered fully representative of the entire student population in Romania. The distribution by residence background, education levels and professional status is relatively balanced, but wider demographic and socio-economic variations were not fully captured. Thus, conclusions cannot be generalized without caution to all students in Romania. Data collection took place in a limited period (March 15 - April 15, 2024), which may influence perceptions depending on the specific socio-political context of the time. Recent political or social events may have a significant impact on participants' responses. Thus, the survey findings may to some extent reflect temporary conditions rather than a stable and generalized perception.

A significant limitation of this study is related to the method of data collection using an online questionnaire. The use of an online questionnaire may introduce some degree of bias into the sample, as not all students have equal access to the internet or are equally comfortable with the use of technology. This may exclude certain segments of the student population, particularly those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds or from rural areas with limited internet access (Andrade, 2020). The questionnaire also had the possibility of being redistributed by respondents. This method may introduce a self-selection bias, as respondents who choose to answer and redistribute the questionnaire may have certain similar characteristics or opinions (Ball, 2019). Thus, this may lead to an uneven sample where participants share common traits, thus distorting the representativeness and generalizability of the results.

Conclusions

Our study has highlighted the importance of education, adequate information and understanding socio-demographic factors in reducing support for nationalist parties and strengthening democratic values among young people. Education plays a central role in shaping critical thinking and a deep understanding of democratic principles. Students with higher educational attainment demonstrated more negative perceptions of nationalist parties and more robust support for democratic values, underlining the need to invest in civic education at all levels of education. Thus, education not only improves theoretical knowledge but also develops young people's ability to analyze and critique nationalist political rhetoric.

Adequate information is also crucial for the formation of political opinion. Access to quality and credible information enables young people to develop informed opinions and be more skeptical of nationalist rhetoric. Disinformation and fake news are major threats to democracy and preventing them is essential to maintain an informed and healthy public space.

Socio-demographic factors such as age, gender and residential background play a significant role in shaping political perceptions. Our study found that young people, women and those in urban areas have different perceptions of nationalist parties compared to other demographic groups. For example, women tend to perceive less populism and rising nationalism as threats compared to men, and urban versus rural play a significant role in shaping these perceptions. These differences highlight the need to understand and address the specificities of each demographic segment to effectively promote democratic values.

Civic involvement is another key aspect of sustaining democracy. Active participation of citizens in decision-making processes strengthens democracy and empowers citizens, making them feel part of the decision-making process and more engaged in community life. Our study found that informed young people are better able to recognize and combat populist and nationalist rhetoric while being strong defenders of democratic values. The results of our study therefore emphasize that quality education, access to truthful information and a detailed understanding of socio-demographic diversity are essential to reduce support for nationalist parties and strengthen democratic values. Through an integrated approach, taking all these aspects into account, a healthy and balanced political environment can be created. This will help to develop a generation of young people who not only support democracy but actively participate in strengthening it.

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